

ASHURALI ZAHIRI'S ARTICLE "WHEN WILL IT HAPPEN?" AS A HISTORICAL SOURCE

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Abstract. *In the state brief life of Ashurali Zahiri, one of the national intellectuals of the Fergana Valley, and his new views on the problems that arose in the public life of Turkestan in the late 19th - early 20th centuries. century, illuminated in his state "When it happens".*

Keywords: *jadidism, Ashurali Zahiri, Turkestan, darkness, ignorance, illiteracy, education, enlightenment, book, "usuli savtiya", renewal, science, development.*

INTRODUCTION

Ashurali Zahiri (1885-1937) at the beginning of the 20th century worked within the framework of his profession to renew the life of society and rebuild it based on the requirements of the times and spared no effort in this regard. He was one of the modern enlighteners who set themselves the goal of reforming human consciousness and thinking through the development of education, bringing colonial Turkestan into the ranks of developed countries in the world through reforms.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Ashurali Zahiri is a well-known modern scholar, enlightener, linguist, journalist, translator, lexicographer and scholar of literature. One of the national intellectuals of the Fergana Valley, a prominent figure of the Jadidist movement. He was born in 1885 in the village of Oyim near the city of Ko'kan. Like all people of his time, he received his primary education in an old school. In 1897-1914, he studied at the Madrasa of Muhammad Ali Khan (that is, Madali Khan) in Kokand. During his studies at the madrasa, he studied religious knowledge, as well as history, language, and literature, including Arabic, Persian, Azerbaijani, Turkish, Tatar, and Russian languages, as well as Persian-Tajik classical literature. Ashurali Zahiri, who acquired comprehensive knowledge, taught language and literature in the school of the Russian system between 1907 (from March 9) and 1917, as well as in the modern school. He teaches as a teacher in courses and schools for the elimination of illiteracy, at the Kokan Pedagogical Institute, and encourages people to learn languages and become knowledgeable. In the years 1908-1913, Ashurali Zahiri opened a new school of Darulmu'allimin in the city of Kokand. He used samples of classic Uzbek and Eastern literature during his education. He also works at the Fergana Pedagogical Technical College, headed by Qori Niazi in Fergana. Here Ashurali Zahiri works together with pedagogues such as Bulat Soliev, Hodi Fayzi, Qori Niazi. His teaching career continued until 1919.

RESEARCH RESULTS

During his career, Ashurali Zahiri tried to show the social situation among the population and their certain strata with his modern views through a series of articles he wrote. Another article of the author, published on May 23, 1914, was published in "Sadoyi Ferghana" newspaper, "When will it be?" is an article called In the article, the author admits that the people of Turkestan are unaware of world development and worldly news, and tries to reveal the attitude of the people of Turkestan to science, books, development and progress. Therefore, he spoke about the level of

acceptance of development in the Islamic world at such a time, and it is like collecting millions of books in all fields of science, putting one of our people in this library and reading the books in this library and acquiring some knowledge. they said, we careless servants were lazy and did not use it, we could not use it. In any case, we were satisfied with what we had. We are going this way for a long time - he writes¹. With this, the author criticizes the fact that Muslim countries are lagging behind other countries in terms of development, and instead of developing science and benefiting from it, they are busy feeding themselves and making ends meet.

Why did the author express such opinions? Because, in his opinion, if a Muslim is needed for the work of his time, including office work, or if a person is looking for a teacher for the Sawtiya school, schools like Rashidi, Avloni, which are opened due to the permission of the state, if a person is given permission to publish a newspaper and he if an editor is needed, if an accountant is needed for the property that is being opened everywhere, if a candidate is asked to participate in the State Duma of All-Russia Muslims, in the Petersburg Council, he admits that even if he searches for ten years with a light during the day, he will not find suitable people. The author concludes that it is known from such cases that we are not aware of modern science and culture. Even if we were not aware, life had to compel. But when faced with various hardships, we have stopped and left the roads that we used to pass with pleasure to the extent that our eyes are not afraid of them, and our minds are not enough. We haven't moved further or since, we have been moving for a long time, but it seems that a lot of time will have to pass before moving forward. But when will it be! , - exclaims the author. Addressing his compatriots with this article, the representative of Jadid, who can benefit his country, nation, identity, family, and himself, when will the experts in all fields come out, when will the nation, the country, and science develop and achieve progress. It raises questions about when Muslim people will achieve a comfortable standard of living. And in this regard, it shows that a number of reforms should be carried out in the country.

Although hundreds of years have passed, our people are still experiencing the processes of development and renewal in social life in our country. This article, which was brought to the attention of our nation so long ago, has not lost its importance as a historical source and has not been included in the scope of special research. That is why we converted it from the old Uzbek script to the current script, prepared it for publication and are bringing it to the attention of researchers.

When will it be?

If we look at the paths that have passed since the beginning of time, the human child is improving and developing in every way day by day and year by year.

In the free world of Mr. Haq, every person is finding the feelings created for each individual, even if it is obediently, and he is producing many famous and favorable signs and habits in the new year. We don't know what will be invented in a few more years? What do you accept? But this will not be a progressive and perfect mansukh (fortunate person V.K.) and all the creations (acceptable) that have been discovered by the servants in the divine treasure of Mr. Haq will not be finished until the world of crisis.

Nowadays, we, the Islamic world, are like that, there are millions of all kinds of subjects. This library is yours, if you want any kind of book, you can find it and use it if you want. Even if you don't want to use it, try it. But if you gain knowledge using these books, we will increase your rank and rank accordingly. Otherwise, we will give your time at the level of power laymut (V.K.

in the sense of providing food at the level of immortality). Samodin is like a person who has been brought to the door of bliss. In this world of life, Mr. Haq regularly creates a treasure that does not have this little "no" and goes to its dark lands, or goes to his presence and blesses all our deeds. .K.) even if he sent us to our hands, we could not and did not think to use the lazy slave (Islamic world). In any case, our stomachs are full of cash, so we are satisfied with it. In this way, we are going for an indefinite number of times.

That's why, if you need one person for one of the jobs of the present time (that is, if you need a Muslim to stand in place of him), then a school of the one-hearted method, or Rashidi, Avloni schools are being built with the official permission. If the teachers want, or if they want to publish a newspaper and magazine, they will give it to the editorial board, if they need an editor. Perhaps, in those days, the small loan houses (property credit) that are opening everywhere need an accountant (uchetevod), or in those days, they are called to send a deputation to the meeting of the council in Petersburg, which was authorized by the internal control of the affairs of all-Russian Muslims, or if, by the decree of our tsar, the Gosudarstvenny Duma is elected, Sara, Saraga, if you need a decent breed, you won't be able to find it even if you want ten years with a light during the day.

But if you want to be an imam and a muezzin in a local mosque, or if you want to place a candle on top of someone's grave, or if you need a person to do something like that, you have to ask for a new one! it causes quarrels and quarrels between several people. However, it is doubtful that you will earn one hundred soums per year.

It is clear from these cases that we are not aware of modern science and culture. Even if we didn't want to be aware, life had to force us. But what is the happiness and bliss that we do not see with our eyes even if we face various hardships in life? in what We have become so stubborn that our minds are not enough. We haven't been able to move forward or since, we have been and continue to be, but it seems that a lot of time has to pass before we can move forward. But when will it be?

DISCUSSION

There are more than 25 articles of Ashurali Zahiri, a prominent representative of Turkestan moderns, which serve to illuminate the country's social, political, spiritual, educational, linguistic, historical, and scientific fields. We did not dwell on his other articles, as the research focused on his article "When Will it be". His articles can be found in "Gazette of the Turkistan Region", "Sadoyi Ferghana" and other newspapers of the same period.

CONCLUSION

Ashurali Zahiri, a Jadid luminary, who was born in the city of Ko'qan of the Fergana Valley, worked in the field of science, education, upbringing, spirituality, and enlightenment. among people, he will remain forever in history and in the memory of today's generations with his services.

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